

Yoga Prana Vidya (YPV) Healing as an Integrative Approach in the Management of Jaundice: A Case Study

Padma Srinivasu¹, Venkata Satyanarayana Nanduri²

¹YPV Certified Healer & Senior YPV Trainer, Bengaluru, Karnataka, India

²Consultant, Research & Publications, YPV Ashram, Sri Ramana Trust, Thally-635118, Tamil Nadu, India

KEYWORDS:

Yoga Prana Vidya System ®, YPV ®, Jaundice, Complementary Therapy, Integrative Healing

Corresponding Author:

Venkata Satyanarayana Nanduri

DOI: [10.55677/IJMSPR/2026-3050-I302](https://doi.org/10.55677/IJMSPR/2026-3050-I302)

Published: March 17, 2026

License:

This is an open access article under the CC BY 4.0 license:
<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>

ABSTRACT

Background: Jaundice is a clinical manifestation of underlying hepatic dysfunction, often requiring medical intervention. Complementary therapies such as Yoga Prana Vidya (YPV) have shown promise in accelerating recovery and improving patient cooperation with conventional treatment.

Objective: To document the role of YPV healing techniques in the recovery of a patient with jaundice, highlighting clinical progress and psychosocial outcomes.

Method: Case presentation: A 67-year-old male patient diagnosed with jaundice presented with fever, weakness, drowsiness, lack of appetite, and reluctance to undergo hospital-based investigations. YPV healing was initiated on 2nd December 2025, employing YPV Level 2 & 3 protocols including internal organ cleansing, blood cleansing, infection protocol and psychotherapy. Post YPV healing intervention, he agreed for hospital admission. YPV healing sessions were conducted twice daily for 20 minutes over 16 days.

Results: Within three days, the patient demonstrated improved cooperation and energy. By day six, appetite improved, and by day twelve, energy levels normalized. Clinical reports indicated stabilization, leading to hospital discharge. Sustained improvements were noted in appetite, feeding, and daily activities.

Conclusion: YPV healing facilitated patient acceptance of medical care, improved clinical outcomes, and enhanced psychosocial well-being. This case supports the integration of YPV as a complementary modality in hepatic dysfunction management.

Cite the Article: Srinivasu, P., Nanduri, V.S. (2026). Yoga Prana Vidya (YPV) Healing as an Integrative Approach in the Management of Jaundice: A Case Study. *International Journal of Medical Science and Pharmaceutical Research*, 3(3), 92–96.
<https://doi.org/10.55677/IJMSPR/2026-3050-I302>

INTRODUCTION

Jaundice, characterized by yellowing of the skin and sclera due to elevated bilirubin levels, is a common clinical manifestation of hepatic dysfunction. When liver dysfunctions, bile duct obstructions, or excessive destruction of red blood cells occurs, bilirubin builds up in the bloodstream, resulting in jaundice. Jaundice itself is not a disease but indicates underlying medical issues that can range from mild infections to serious liver conditions. It can affect people of all ages, including infants and adults, and necessitates appropriate diagnosis and treatment to avoid complications. Jaundice is not a disease but potential causes include liver diseases, infections, genetic disorders, or blockages in the bile ducts. In many situations, jaundice may signify serious health concerns, such as hepatitis, cirrhosis, or gallbladder issues. Timely diagnosis and treatment are crucial to prevent complications and ensure proper care [1-3].

Conventional management involves diagnostic evaluation, pharmacological treatment, and supportive care. However, patient compliance and psychosocial factors often influence recovery. Integrative approaches combining conventional medicine with complementary therapies are increasingly recognized for their holistic benefits [4].

Yoga Prana Vidya (YPV) is an energy-based healing system that employs pranic energy techniques, meditation, and forgiveness practices to restore balance and vitality. It is an integrated and holistic system which is known for no drug and no touch process which can be applied in distance mode as well [5-6]. Literature shows over 160 published research articles documenting its efficacy in diverse applications such as physical health, mental health and spiritual health. Previous studies have documented YPV's role in managing chronic conditions, enhancing emotional resilience, and improving physiological outcomes [7- 15]. Studies on liver health improvements using YPV successfully have also appeared in the literature [17-18].

The present study explores the application of YPV healing in a male patient aged 67 years with jaundice, focusing on clinical progress, patient cooperation, and psychosocial outcomes.

METHOD

Case Presentation

Patient Information:

- Age: 67 years
- Gender: Male
- Occupation: Agriculture
- Location: India

Pre-YPV Medical Condition:

On 2nd December 2025, the patient presented with fever, tiredness, weakness, drowsiness, yellow sclera, bloating, flatulence, and lack of appetite. He was afraid of hospitals and reluctant to undergo diagnostic tests, complicating medical management. His blood report dated 02 December 2025 is at Annexure 1 which shows high level of Bilirubin (13.4 mg/Dl). His relative encouraged him to consider YPV healing sessions from a Certified YPV Healer, to which he was willing. Stenting and biopsy were done in the Hospital on 03 December 2025.

YPV Healing Intervention:

- The Certified Healer initiated the YPV intervention on 2nd December 2025
- Protocols used: Level 3 psychotherapy, internal organ cleansing, blood cleansing, infection protocol
- Session Frequency and duration: Twice daily, 20 minutes per session
- Length of intervention: 16 days (ending 18th December 2025)

Patient Progress:

- Day 1: Acceptance of medical tests, improved cooperation with family
- Day 3: Increased energy levels
- Day 6: Improved appetite and interest in food
- Day 9: Normalization of feeding patterns
- Day 12: Enhanced vitality and normalized activities
- Day 14: Blood test shows Bilirubin level near to normal (Annexure 2).
- Day 16: Clinical outcome normal, and discharged from hospital (Discharge summary is at Annexure 3)

RESULTS

The patient demonstrated progressive improvement in both physical and psychosocial parameters. Notably, YPV healing facilitated acceptance of medical interventions, reduced fear, and improved cooperation. Appetite and energy levels improved steadily, leading to normalization of daily activities. Clinical reports confirmed stabilization, and the patient was discharged in a stable condition. Follow-up indicated sustained improvements.

DISCUSSION

This case highlights the potential of YPV healing as a complementary modality in managing jaundice. Several mechanisms may explain the observed outcomes:

1. *Energy Cleansing:* YPV protocols aim to remove congested energy, which may correlate with improved physiological functioning.
2. *Psychosocial Impact:* Healing sessions reduced fear and resistance, enabling patient cooperation with medical care.
3. *Holistic Recovery:* Improvements in appetite, energy, and emotional state suggest systemic benefits beyond symptomatic relief.

Comparable studies have documented YPV's efficacy in managing diabetes, hypertension, and psychosomatic conditions. Integrating YPV with conventional medicine may enhance recovery, reduce hospital stay, and improve patient compliance.

Despite the limitation of this study being a single case study, it offers scope for further studies using appropriate sample.

Future Directions:

Controlled clinical trials with larger samples are needed to validate YPV's efficacy in hepatic dysfunction. Psychometric scales assessing fear, compliance, and quality of life may provide quantitative insights.

CONCLUSION

YPV healing contributed significantly to the recovery of a jaundice patient by improving clinical outcomes, patient cooperation, and psychosocial well-being. This case supports the integration of YPV as a complementary therapy in hepatic dysfunction management.

Acknowledgments

The authors thank the patient and family for their cooperation, and the YPV community for guidance and support.

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Funding

No external funding was received for this study.

REFERENCES

1. Joseph A, Samant H. Jaundice. 2023 Aug 8. In: StatPearls [Internet]. Treasure Island (FL): StatPearls Publishing; 2025 Jan-. PMID: 31334972.
2. Shrihari Nighot*, Ankita Jadhav, Swati Deshmukh, A Clinical Case Study on Jaundice: Causes, Diagnosis, Treatment, Management and Public Awareness, *Int. J. of Pharm. Sci.*, 2025, Vol 3, Issue 5, 2816-2833. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1544892>
3. Gofur NRP, Gofur ARP, Soesilaningtyas, Gofur RNR, Kahdina M, et al. Jaundice Clinical Manifestation and Pathophysiology: A Review Article. *J Clin Images*. 2022; 5(1): 1111.
4. Gunathilake, S & Alvis, Kapila & Gunawardana, K & Rajapaksha, Sandya & Warnakulasooriya, A & Athulgama, P & Dius, Sanjeewa & Ranwala, R & Bandara, Sau & Godage, Sanjaya & Pn, Rodrigo & Vidanagama, U & Fernando, C & Ekanayake, U & Hapuarachchi, T & Gunasena, P & Aluthge, P & Abeyak, Mud. (2025). Understanding Jaundice Pathophysiology and Clinical Implications. 10.13140/RG.2.2.10544.47362.
5. Neravetla JR, Nanduri VS. Integrative Health Practices and Holistic Health: The Role of the Integrated Yoga Prana Vidya (YPV) System as Complementary and alternative medicine. *Advances in Integrative Health Practices*, 2025;1(1)-31-38
6. N J Reddy, Nanduri VS. Role of Yoga Prana Vidya (YPV) system in the successful management of metabolic diseases: A Review, *IP Journal of Nutrition, Metabolism and Health Science*, 2024; 7(4):136-140 <https://www.jnmhs.com/article-details/23404> <https://doi.org/10.18231/j.ijnmhs.2024.025>
7. Padma Srinivasu, Hitesh Kumara, Nanduri VS. Integrative energy healing for cervical insufficiency in pregnancy: A case study on Yoga Prana Vidya (YPV) intervention, *International Journal of Medicine Research*, 2026;11(01):23-25
8. Baliga M, Nanduri VS. Yoga Prana Vidya Healing in the Management of Migraine: A Case Study of a 15-Year-Old Female. *International Journal of Medical Science and Applied Research (IJMSAR)*, 2026;09(01):01-05
9. Padma Srinivasu. Nanduri VS. Yoga Prana Vidya Healing as Complementary Medicine in Scalp Psoriasis: A Case Report. *Int J of Med Sci & Health Res*, 2026;10(01):154-159 doi: 10.51505/ijmshr.2026.1012
10. [10] Dholakia MD, Ramnani K. Successful Healing Treatment of Lumbar Scoliosis – The Spinal Postural Deformity Using Yoga Prana Vidya (YPV) System. *IJMESH*, 2026;10(01):119-131
11. Kataria R, Nanduri VS. Speedy Recovery from Transverse Myelitis through Yoga Prana Vidya (YPV) Healing as Complementary Therapy: A Case Study. *Int j of Medical Science and Dental Health*, 2026;12(02):08-18, DOI: <https://doi.org/10.55640/ijmsdh-12-01-06>
12. Baliga M, Nanduri VS. Sustained remission of sciatica (left lumbar radiculopathy) through Yoga Prana Vidya healing as alternative therapy: A 9-year follow-up case study. *International Journal of Medicine Research*, 2025;11(01): 15-18
13. Dholakia M, Ramnani K. Successful Healing Treatment of Gangrene cases using Yoga Prana Vidya (YPV) System. *International Journal of Medicine Research*, 2026; 11(01):9-14
14. Srinivasu P, Nanduri VS. Integrative Role of Yoga Prana Vidya (YPV) Healing in Post-Surgical Recovery of Hip Fracture: A Case Report. *ijmsdh* [Internet]. 2026 Jan. 15 [cited 2026 Jan. 15];12(01):41-4. Available <https://doi.org/10.55640/ijmsdh-12-01-06>
15. Bhupinder Kaur Dimple, Nanduri VS. Yoga Prana Vidya (YPV) as a Complementary Approach in Successful Treatment of Throat Ulcers: A Case Report. *International Journal of Medical Science and Dental Research*, 2026;09(01):01-05
16. Chinnusamy M, Sukumar A, Nanduri VS. Role of yoga prana vidya in healing psychosomatic disorders: a multiple case study in a family setting. *Int J Adv Med* 2025;12 (03):315-9. DOI: <https://dx.doi.org/10.18203/2349-3933.ijam20251083>

17. Seema Srivastava, Nanduri VS. Integrative Yoga Prana Vidya (YPV) Healing Support in Treatment of Recurrent Liver Tumor with Cirrhosis and Hepatitis B: A case study. IASR Journal of Med and Pharm Science, 2026; 6(1):13-17
18. Atheesh Kumar M, Saloni Dilip Shah, Nanduri, VS. A Case of Non-Alcoholic Fatty Liver Disease [Nafld]: Successful Treatment Using Yoga Prana Vidya Healing Without Surgical or Medical Intervention. Clinical Medicine And Health Research Journal, 2022; 2(5):183-186 <https://doi.org/10.18535/cmhrj.v2i5.81>

ANNEXURES

Annexure 1: Blood report of LFT dated 02 December 2025

DEPARTMENT OF BIOCHEMISTRY			
Patient Name : Mr. RAMAKRISHNAMA NAIDU DAMA		Age/Gender : 67 Y(s) / Male	
Bill Date : 02-Dec-2025 08:20 AM		Admn/UMR No : IP8344 / UMR00027973	
Received Date : 02-Dec-2025 8:20 AM		Bill No/Result No : SER0128491 / RES50664	
Report Date : 02-Dec-2025 08:54 AM		Ward/Room/Bed :	
Ref By : DR.PAVAN CHANDHAR DUDDE M.B.B.S, M.S, FNAS, FIA		Org.Name : GO DIGIT GENERAL INSURANCE	
		Specimen : BLOOD	
Parameter	Result Values	Biological Reference	Method
Liver Function Tests (LFT)			
BILIRUBIN TOTAL	* 13.4 MG/DL	0.3 - 1.2 MG/DL	
BILIRUBIN DIRECT	* 5.6 MG/DL	0.1 - 0.30 MG/DL	
BILIRUBIN INDIRECT	* 7.8 MG/DL	< 0.80 MG/DL	
AST/SGOT	* 194 U/L	0 - 35 U/L	
ALT/SGPT	* 233 U/L	0 - 45 U/L	
Alkaline Phosphatase	* 336 U/L	30.0 - 120.0 U/L	IFCC/DGKCh kinetic
TOTAL PROTEINS	6.1 G/DL	6.0 - 8.0 G/DL	
SERUM ALBUMIN	3.5 G/DL	3.5 - 5.5 G/DL	
SERUM GLOBULIN	2.6 G/DL	2.0 - 3.5 G/DL	EM 200
A/G Ratio	1		
GAMMA GLUTAMYL TRANSFERASE	* 98 U/L	0 - 55 U/L	
*** End Of Report ***			

Annexure 2 Blood report dated 14 December 2025

DEPARTMENT OF BIOCHEMISTRY			
Patient Name : Mr. RAMAKRISHNAMA NAIDU DAMA		Age / Gender : 67 Y(s) / Male	
Bill Date : 14-Dec-2025 07:42 PM		Admn / UMR No : IP8344 / UMR00027973	
Received Date : 14-Dec-2025 7:42 PM		Bill No / Result No : SER0130639 / RES51538	
Report Date : 14-Dec-2025 08:00 PM		Ward/Room/Bed :	
Ref By : DR.PAVAN CHANDHAR DUDDE M.B.B.S, M.S, FNAS, FIA		Org.Name : GO DIGIT GENERAL INSURANCE	
		Specimen : BLOOD	
Parameter	Result Values	Biological Reference	Method
Liver Function Tests (LFT)			
BILIRUBIN TOTAL	* 1.5 MG/DL	0.3 - 1.2 MG/DL	
BILIRUBIN DIRECT	* 0.4 MG/DL	0.1 - 0.30 MG/DL	
BILIRUBIN INDIRECT	* 1.1 MG/DL	< 0.80 MG/DL	
AST/SGOT	19 U/L	0 - 35 U/L	
ALT/SGPT	23 U/L	0 - 45 U/L	
Alkaline Phosphatase	96 U/L	30.0 - 120.0 U/L	IFCC/DGKCh kinetic
TOTAL PROTEINS	6.5 G/DL	6.0 - 8.0 G/DL	
SERUM ALBUMIN	3.6 G/DL	3.5 - 5.5 G/DL	
SERUM GLOBULIN	2.9 G/DL	2.0 - 3.5 G/DL	EM 200
A/G Ratio	1		
GAMMA GLUTAMYL TRANSFERASE	42 U/L	0 - 55 U/L	
*** End Of Report ***			

Annexure 3: Discharge doc dated 16 Dec 2025

